

Ten limit cycles in a quintic Lyapunov system

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Abstract—In this paper, center conditions and bifurcation of limit cycles at the nilpotent critical point in a class of quintic polynomial differential system are investigated. With the help of computer algebra system MATHEMATICA, the first 10 quasi Lyapunov constants are deduced. As a result, sufficient and necessary conditions in order to have a center are obtained. The fact that there exist 10 small amplitude limit cycles created from the three order nilpotent critical point is also proved. Henceforth we give a lower bound of cyclicity of three-order nilpotent critical point for quintic Lyapunov systems. At last, we give an system which could bifurcate 10 limit circles.

Keywords—Three-order nilpotent critical point, Center-focus problem, Bifurcation of limit cycles, Quasi-Lyapunov constant.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE nilpotent center problem was theoretically solved by Moussu [10] and Stróżyńska [12]. Nevertheless, in fact, given an analytic system with a monodromic point, it is very difficult to know if it is a focus or a center, even in the case of polynomial systems of a given degree. In this paper, we consider an autonomous planar ordinary differential equation having a three-order nilpotent critical point with the form

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dx}{dt} &= y + a_{12}xy^2 + a_{03}y^3 + a_{31}x^3y + a_{22}x^2y^2 \\ &\quad - 4b_{04}xy^3 + a_{04}y^4 - y(x^2 + y^2)^2, \\ \frac{dy}{dt} &= -2x^3 + b_{21}x^2y + b_{03}y^3 + b_{40}x^4 - \frac{3}{2}a_{31}x^2y^2 \\ &\quad + b_{13}xy^3 + b_{04}y^4 + x(x^2 + y^2)^2. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $\mu \neq 0$, and all parameters are real.

In some suitable coordinates, the Lyapunov system with the origin as a nilpotent critical point can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dx}{dt} &= y + \sum_{i+j=2}^{\infty} a_{ij}x^i y^j = X(x, y), \\ \frac{dy}{dt} &= \sum_{i+j=2}^{\infty} b_{ij}x^i y^j = Y(x, y). \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Suppose that the function $y = y(x)$ satisfies $X(x, y) = 0, y(0) = 0$. Lyapunov proved (see for instance [3]) that the origin of system (2) is a monodromic critical point (i.e., a center or a focus) if and only if

$$\begin{aligned} Y(x, y(x)) &= \alpha x^{2n+1} + o(x^{2n+1}), \alpha < 0 \\ \left[\frac{\partial X}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial Y}{\partial x} \right]_{y=y(x)} &= \beta x^n + o(x^n), \\ \beta^2 + 4(n+1)\alpha &< 0, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where n is a positive integer. The monodromy problem in this case was solved in [4] and the center problem in [10], see also in [12]. As far as we know there are essentially three differential ways of obtaining the Lyapunov constant: by using normal form theory [8], by computing the Poincaré return map [6] or by using Lyapunov functions [11]. Álvarez

study the momodromy and stability for nilpotent critical points with the method of computing the Poincaré return map, see for instance [1]; Chavarriga study the local analytic integrability for nilpotent centers by using Lyapunov functions, see for instance [7]; Moussu study the center-focus problem of nilpotent critical points with the method of normal form theory, see for instance [10]. Takens proved in [13] that system (2) can be formally transformed into a generalized Liénard system. Álvarez proved in [2] that using a reparametrization of the time to simplify even more. Giacomini et al. in [14] prove that the analytic nilpotent systems with a center can be expressed as limit of systems non-degenerated with a center. therefore, any nilpotent center can be detected using the same methods that for a nondegenerate center, for instance the Poincaré-Lyapunov method can be used to find the nilpotent centers.

For a given family of polynomial differential equations, let $N(n)$ be the maximum possible number of limit cycles bifurcating from nilpotent critical points for analytic vector fields of degree n . In [5] it is found that $N(3) \geq 2, N(5) \geq 5, N(7) \geq 9$; In [1] it is found that $N(3) \geq 3, N(5) \geq 5$; For a family of Kukles system with 6 parameters, in [2] it is found that $N(3) \geq 3$. Hence in this paper. Recently, Liu Yirong and Li Jibin in [15] proved that $N(3) \geq 8$. Hence in this paper, employing the integral factor method introduced in [9], we will prove $N(5) \geq 10$. To the best of our knowledge, our results on the lower bounds of cyclicity of three-order nilpotent critical points for quintic systems are new.

We will organize this paper as follows. In Section 2, using the linear recursive formulae in [15] to do direct computation, we obtain with relative ease the first 10 quasi-Lyapunov constants and the sufficient and necessary conditions of center. This paper is ended with Section 3 in which the 10-order weak focus conditions and the fact that there exist 10 limit cycles in the neighborhood of the three-order nilpotent critical point are proved.

II. QUASI-LYAPUNOV CONSTANTS AND CENTER CONDITIONS

According to Theorem in [9], for system (1). Carrying out calculations in MATHEMATICA, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_3 &= \omega_4 = \omega_5 = 0, \\ \omega_6 &= -\frac{1}{3}b_{21}(-1 + 4s), \\ \omega_7 &\sim 3(s+1)c_{03}, \\ \omega_8 &\sim -\frac{2(a_{12}+3b_{03})}{5}(-3 + 4s), \\ \omega_9 &\sim -\frac{2(2a_{22}+3b_{13})}{3}(-1 + s). \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

From (3.1), we obtain the first two quasi-Lyapunov constants of system (1):

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_1 &= \frac{\omega_6}{1-4s} = \frac{b_{21}}{3}, \\ \lambda_2 &\sim \frac{\omega_8}{3-4s} = \frac{2(a_{12}+3b_{03})}{5}. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

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we see from $\omega_7 = \omega_9 = 0$ that

$$c_{03} = 0, s = 1. \quad (6)$$

Furthermore, take $s = 1$, we obtain the following conclusion.

Proposition 2.1: For system (1), one can determine successively the terms of the formal series $M(x, y) = x^4 + y^2 + o(r^4)$, such that

$$\left(\frac{\partial X}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial Y}{\partial y}\right)M - 2\left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial x}X + \frac{\partial M}{\partial y}Y\right) = \sum_{m=1}^{11} \lambda_m [(2m - 5)x^{2m+4} + o(r^{28})], \quad (7)$$

where λ_m is the m -th quasi-Lyapunov constant at the origin of system (1), $m = 1, 2, \dots, 12$.

Theorem 2.1: For system (1), the first 12 quasi-Lyapunov constants at the origin are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_1 &= \frac{b_{21}}{3}, \\ \lambda_2 &= \frac{2(a_{12} + 3b_{03})}{5}, \\ \lambda_3 &= \frac{b_{40}(2a_{22} + 3b_{13})}{35}, \\ \lambda_4 &= -\frac{(2a_{22} + 3b_{13})a_{31}}{15}, \\ \lambda_5 &= \frac{20b_{04}(2a_{22} + 3b_{13})}{77}, \\ \lambda_6 &= \frac{-4b_{03}(172a_{22} - 13b_{13})(2a_{22} + 3b_{13})}{3003}, \\ \lambda_7 &= \frac{8b_{03}(41067a_{04} - 7658a_{22})(2a_{22} + 3b_{13})}{405405}, \\ \lambda_8 &= \frac{112(160681 + 733941a_{03})a_{22}b_{03}(2a_{22} + 3b_{13})}{45379035}, \\ \lambda_9 &= \frac{4a_{22}b_{03}(2a_{22} + 3b_{13})}{6240681974475}(-9539331965897 \\ &\quad + 20127128261760b_{03}^2), \\ \lambda_{10} &= \frac{-a_{22}b_{03}(2a_{22} + 3b_{13})}{188992023730839771840450}(632226312156980494004945 \\ &\quad + 815899547527119916257024a_{22}^2) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

In the above expression of λ_k , we have already let $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \dots = \lambda_{k-1} = 0$, $k = 2, \dots, 10$.

From Theorem 2.1, we obtain the following assertion.

Proposition 2.2: The first 10 quasi-Lyapunov constants at the origin of system (1) are zero if and only if the following condition is satisfied:

$$b_{21} = a_{31} = b_{03} = b_{40} = b_{04} = a_{12} = 0; \quad (9)$$

$$b_{21} = 0, a_{12} = -3b_{03}, a_{22} = -\frac{3}{2}b_{13}. \quad (10)$$

Proof. When condition (9) of Proposition 3.2 holds, system (1) can be brought to

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dx}{dt} &= y + a_{03}y^3 + a_{22}x^2y^2 + a_{04}y^4 - y(x^2 + y^2)^2, \\ \frac{dy}{dt} &= -2x^3 + b_{13}xy^3 + x(x^2 + y^2)^2. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

whose vector field is symmetric with respect to the y -axis.

When condition (10) of Proposition 3.2 holds, system (1) can be brought to

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dx}{dt} &= y + -3b_{03}xy^2 + a_{03}y^3 + a_{31}x^3y - \frac{3}{2}b_{13}x^2y^2 \\ &\quad - 4b_{04}xy^3 + a_{04}y^4 - y(x^2 + y^2)^2, \\ \frac{dy}{dt} &= -2x^3 + b_{03}y^3 + b_{40}x^4 - \frac{3}{2}a_{31}x^2y^2 + b_{13}xy^3 \\ &\quad + b_{04}y^4 + x(x^2 + y^2)^2. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

the system (12) has an analytic first integral

$$\begin{aligned} H(x, y) &= -\frac{1}{2}y^2 - \frac{1}{2}x^4 - \frac{1}{2}a_{31}x^3y^2 + \frac{1}{2}b_{13}x^2y^3 + b_{04}xy^4 \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{4}a_{03}y^4 - \frac{1}{5}a_{04}y^5 + b_{03}xy^3 + \frac{1}{3}(x^2 + y^2)^3. \end{aligned}$$

□

We see from Propositions 2.2 that

Theorem 2.2: The origin of system (1) is a center if and only if the first 10 quasi-Lyapunov constants are zero, that is, one of the conditions in Proposition 2.2 is satisfied.

III. MULTIPLE BIFURCATION OF LIMIT CYCLES

This section is devoted proving that when the three-order nilpotent critical point $O(0, 0)$ is a 10-order weak focus, the perturbed system of (1) can generate 10 limit cycles enclosing an elementary node at the origin of perturbation system (1).

Using the fact $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \lambda_3 = \lambda_4 = \lambda_5 = \lambda_6 = \lambda_7 = \lambda_8 = \lambda_9 = 0$, $\lambda_{10} \neq 0$, we obtain

Theorem 3.1: The origin of system (1) is a 10-order weak focus if and only if

$$\begin{aligned} b_{21} &= b_{40} = a_{31} = b_{04} = 0, \\ a_{12} &= -3b_{03}, b_{13} = \frac{171}{13}a_{22}, \\ a_{04} &= \frac{7658}{41067}a_{22}, \\ a_{03} &= -\frac{160681}{733941}, \\ b_{03} &= \pm \sqrt{\frac{9539331965897}{14904}}, a_{22} \neq 0. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Proof. By letting $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \lambda_3 = \lambda_4 = \lambda_5 = \lambda_6 = \lambda_7 = \lambda_8 = \lambda_9 = 0$, we obtain the relations of b_{21} , b_{40} , a_{31} , b_{04} , a_{12} , b_{13} , a_{22} , a_{04} , a_{03} , b_{03} . Because $a_{22} \neq 0$, the origin of system (1) is a 10-order weak focus. □

We next study the perturbed system of (1) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dx}{dt} &= \delta x + y + a_{12}xy^2 + a_{03}y^3 + a_{31}x^3y + a_{22}x^2y^2 \\ &\quad - 4b_{04}xy^3 + a_{04}y^4 - y(x^2 + y^2)^2, \\ \frac{dy}{dt} &= 2\delta y - 2x^3 + b_{21}x^2y + b_{03}y^3 + b_{40}x^4 - \frac{3}{2}a_{31}x^2y^2 \\ &\quad + b_{13}xy^3 + b_{04}y^4 + x(x^2 + y^2)^2. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

When conditions in (13) hold, we have

$$\begin{aligned} J &= \frac{\partial(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, \lambda_4, \lambda_5, \lambda_6, \lambda_7, \lambda_8, \lambda_9)}{\partial(b_{21}, a_{12}, b_{40}, a_{31}, b_{04}, b_{13}, a_{04}, a_{03}, b_{03})} \\ &= \frac{\partial\lambda_1}{\partial b_{21}} \frac{\partial\lambda_2}{\partial a_{12}} \frac{\partial\lambda_3}{\partial b_{40}} \frac{\partial\lambda_4}{\partial a_{31}} \frac{\partial\lambda_5}{\partial b_{04}} \frac{\partial\lambda_6}{\partial b_{13}} \frac{\partial\lambda_7}{\partial a_{04}} \frac{\partial\lambda_8}{\partial a_{03}} \frac{\partial\lambda_9}{\partial b_{03}} \\ &= \frac{4720881626272548607185227793232964573995264a_{22}^9 b_{03}}{4283058355201979039129867771096953125} \\ &\neq 0. \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

The statement mentioned above follows that

Theorem 3.2: If the origin of system (1) is a 10-order weak focus, for $0 < \delta \ll 1$, making a small perturbation to the coefficients of system (1), then, for system (14), in a small neighborhood of the origin, there exist exactly 10 small amplitude limit cycles enclosing the origin $O(0, 0)$, which is an elementary node.

IV. EXAMPLE OF BIFURCATION OF LIMIT CYCLES AT ORIGIN

Now we consider bifurcation of limit cycles at the origin for perturbed system (14).

Theorem 4.1: Suppose that the coefficients of system (14) satisfy

$$\begin{aligned} \delta &= \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon^{55}, b_{21} = 3\varepsilon^{45}, \\ a_{12} &= -\frac{C}{4968} - \frac{243386597004525\varepsilon}{41133599436947864} + \frac{5}{2}\varepsilon^{36}, \\ b_{40} &= \frac{65}{77}\varepsilon^{28}, a_{31} = \frac{195}{539}\varepsilon^{21}, \\ b_{03} &= \frac{13}{140}\varepsilon^{15}, a_{22} = 1, \\ b_{13} &= \frac{171}{13} - \frac{145314C}{7}\varepsilon^{10}, \\ a_{04} &= \frac{7658}{41067} - \frac{40365C}{49}\varepsilon^6, \\ a_{03} &= -\frac{160681}{733941} - \frac{61395165C}{3773}\varepsilon^3, \\ b_{03} &= \frac{1}{1914C} + \frac{81128865668175}{41133599436947864}\varepsilon, \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where $C = \sqrt{\frac{90610}{9539331965897}}$. Then, if $\varepsilon = 0$, the origin of system (14) is an tenth fine focus with stability. If $0 < \varepsilon \ll 1$, there exist ten limit cycles in a small enough neighborhood of the origin of system (14).

Proof. According to Theorem 2.1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} v_1(2\pi, \delta) &= -\varepsilon^{55} + O(\varepsilon^{55}), \\ v_2(2\pi, \delta) &= \varepsilon^{45} + O(\varepsilon^{45}), \\ v_3(2\pi, \delta) &= -\varepsilon^{36} + O(\varepsilon^{36}), \\ v_4(2\pi, \delta) &= \varepsilon^{28} - \frac{5667246C}{3773}\varepsilon^{38} + O(\varepsilon^{38}), \\ v_5(2\pi, \delta) &= -\varepsilon^{21} + \frac{5667246C}{3773}\varepsilon^{31} + O(\varepsilon^{31}), \\ v_6(2\pi, \delta) &= \varepsilon^{15} - \frac{5667246C}{3773}\varepsilon^{25} + O(\varepsilon^{25}), \\ v_7(2\pi, \delta) &= -\varepsilon^{10} - \frac{151143076739810025C}{5141699929618483}\varepsilon^{11} + O(\varepsilon^{11}), \\ v_8(2\pi, \delta) &= \varepsilon^6 + \frac{151143076739810025C}{5141699929618483}\varepsilon^7 + O(\varepsilon^7), \\ v_9(2\pi, \delta) &= -\varepsilon^3 - \frac{151143076739810025C}{5141699929618483}\varepsilon^4 \\ &\quad + \frac{5667246C}{3773}\varepsilon^{13} + O(\varepsilon^{13}), \\ v_{10}(2\pi, \delta) &= \varepsilon + \frac{151143076739810025C}{5141699929618483}\varepsilon^2 \\ &\quad - \frac{5667246C}{3773}\varepsilon^{11} + O(\varepsilon^{11}), \\ v_{11}(2\pi, \delta) &= -\frac{780539838369730121131201291C}{36617582581897667473630868400} \\ &\quad - \frac{1448125859684100410261969}{2311103383443064036777392}\varepsilon + O(\varepsilon), \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Because the sign of the focal values of the origin has reversed eleven times, from Theorem in [15] there exist ten limit cycles in a small enough neighborhood of the origin of system (14). \square

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